

Copperplates in Context: A Preliminary Investigation of the Study and Archaeological Settings of Land Grant Inscriptions

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Abstract

The fourth to the seventh centuries C.E., commonly referred to as the “Gupta Era”, are widely regarded as a formative period in South Asian history. Textual historical approaches to the study of this period have focussed on the examination of inscriptions, which constitute the largest single source of evidence. One group of inscriptions, the copperplate charters, have proved particularly important. They not only record the practice of royal land grants to Brahmins and temple institutions, but also embody wider processes of political legitimization, religious transformation and socio-economic change. Thus far, however, studies have focussed on the texts of these inscriptions, which remain divorced from the contexts that produced them and in which they were used. Arguing for an archaeological approach to the study of these charters, this paper demonstrates the value of investigating their geographical and archaeological contexts—first, by mapping the find spots of these charters across the subcontinent; and second, by exploring the archaeological settings of these find spots in one particular region: Vidarbha. The results of this work have clear implications for the future study of these and other inscriptions, and suggest new directions for archaeological approaches to the study of historical periods.

Introduction

The period from c. the fourth to the seventh centuries C.E. is widely recognised as one of great change across South Asia. During this time, we know that there were significant transformations in the economic, social and political spheres. These developments included: the proliferation and spread of Brahmanical sects (Pranabananda 1974; cf. Bakker 2011; Bisschop 2010; Willis 2009), and changes in the nature of the polity, kingship and the mechanisms of political power (Ali 2004; Kulke 2001). Closely linked to these changes were: the increased strength of temple institutions (Chattopadhyaya 2003), a supposed intensification of agriculture (Chattopadhyaya 1994), florescence of arts (Williams 1982), and the widespread adoption and use of Sanskrit across the subcontinent (Pollock 2006). These societal transformations are reflected by a wide range of evidence, mainly consisting of monuments, sculptures and texts. Of these, inscriptions have been the main objects and foci of study within historical scholarship (interpreted broadly). They are not only the most numerous of all available sources, but also the most wide ranging in terms of what they say and are able to tell us about the period. Indeed, it has been estimated that approximately 80% of our collective knowledge and understanding of this period is from the inscriptions that were produced during this time (Salamon 1998: 3).

The single largest group of inscriptions that were produced during this period are the copperplate charters. As is well known, this series of inscriptions were engraved on copper plates, and produced in many parts of peninsular South Asia between the fourth and seventh centuries C.E. They record

the grants of land, by kings or (far less commonly) powerful individuals, to temples and other religious institutions, Brahmins, or political subordinates. While the precise wording of these charters varies both regionally and individually from inscription to inscription, the details of the grants are usually very brief. They name the donor and (frequently) the place where the grant was issued from, before detailing: the donee (or donees) together with their religious affiliation, and the nature of the grant. These are usually a plot of land within an existing village, or else an entire village, and the revenue generated from that land. Grants are recorded as being tax-free, and made to increase the merit of the donor. The specifics of each grant are invariably prefixed by lengthy honorifics in poetic Sanskrit verse. These reveal details of the kings and other issuing authorities, their familial relations and political alliances, administrative and territorial divisions of kingdoms, and the Brahmanical sects or other recipients of the grants. To date, there are approximately 243 inscriptions of this type dating to between the fourth and seventh centuries C.E. extant from across South Asia.¹ While their dimensions vary regionally, an example of this type of early charter can be seen in Fig. 1.

The texts of these inscriptions provide us with a great deal of information about various different aspects of the developments that took place during this period. Yet, equally as important as *what* the copperplates say is *how* they have been studied. Usually examined by textual historians and epigraphers, the copperplates have been read in very particular ways. The questions that have been asked of them are only those questions that can and have been framed within fields of textual scholarship, and the way they have been interrogated—with an exclusive focus on their

texts—has very much been dictated by the methods used in textual scholarship. While not for a moment denying the contributions that have been and continue to be made by such studies, this paper argues that the continued study of the copperplates—the single largest corpus of remains for this period—from within a single disciplinary framework limits our understanding of them. Following a review of how scholarship on the copperplate charters has been established, it will be suggested that considering the charters from a more archaeological perspective can provide new directions for the study of both these objects and the period as a whole, specifically: by considering them not only in terms of their textual content, but also as material objects that are signatures of wider practices and societal processes; and by contextualising them in their archaeological and geographical contexts.

Fig. 1: Example of a “Gupta Era” copperplate charter, together with a scale to illustrate their size and portability. Chamak copper plate of Pravarasena II, British Library Oriental Manuscript shelfmark: Ind. Ch. no. 16.

Before continuing, however, it is important to be clear that this paper is not intended to be an in depth review of what scholarship on the copperplates has said. Nor does it make any claims to providing new historical interpretations based on their archaeological contexts. Rather, the point here is more of a methodological one about how they have been approached and studied, along with a suggestion of other productive avenues of enquiry.

Background: Approaches to the Study of Copperplate Charters

Due to both their common occurrence and the information they record, the copperplate charters have long been recognised as an important historical source in modern scholarship. Initially, scholars seized on the fact that their texts contain veritable mines of information that contributed

to the general thrust of enquiry in the fields of political history and religious history (see, for example, Fleet 1888). For over a century they have continued to be an important data set for various developments during the so-called “Gupta Era”, where they are frequently invoked (along with other textual sources) to chart a perceived Gupta suzerainty in various regions (Fleet 1888; Banerji 1933; Gupta 1976), as well as the spread of Brahmanical sects and temple institutions throughout the subcontinent. Subsequently, they were perceived to contain significant information relevant to the study of historical geography, with the identification of the locations of place names mentioned in their texts coming to be established as a legitimate area of enquiry in its own right. This is exemplified by the exhaustive efforts and works of V.V. Mirashi (e.g. Mirashi 1963).

In the mid-twentieth century, the copperplates were invested with additional importance when they began to be read in new ways. Instead of approaching the charters solely in terms of the immediate details contained in their texts, the fact that most recorded not only land grants but also the revenue accrued was interpreted as reflecting a major socio-economic shift. Their collective appearance in the epigraphic record and rapid spread throughout the subcontinent was thus seen as reflecting the emergence of a feudal society (Kosambi 1956; Sharma 1965, 1972). With this, the copperplate charters quickly became central to many works of textual history, being cited by both proponents and detractors of the feudal model (e.g. Sharma 1965; Mukhia 1981).² Along with those copperplates that were produced after the seventh century—in what became the “early medieval” period (Hawkes 2014)—they have continued to constitute a main source of evidence for studies that have attempted to reconstruct the nature of the state and chart changing socio-economic dynamics. This appreciation of the value of the copperplate charters as a category of historical evidence has recently found expression in a number of studies that have consciously focussed on them to reconstruct the changing socio-economic and political dynamics that occurred in particular regions over time (e.g. Ghosh 2015; Singh 1994, Sinha 2001; Shrimali 1990; A. Verma 2007; N. Verma 1992).

The value of the copperplate charters as a category of evidence is thus beyond doubt. As mentioned in the introduction, what is important here is not only what the inscriptions speak of or reflect, but also *how* they have been used as evidence. From this (albeit) brief overview, it is clear that so far the copperplates have been objects of study only within textual scholarship. Within this framework, they have been engaged with and “read” at two different levels: initially as repositories of factual evidence, and more recently as also reflective of changing social dynamics. Yet, despite the undoubted worth of each of these approaches, the charters have tended to be considered as isolated from their original context—both geographical and archaeological. Textual historical studies have rarely

grounded the copperplate charters in space, so we have little idea about how the practices and societal processes reflected in and by the charters actually existed and spread over space and time. Valuable exceptions to this general trend do, of course, exist, with a number of studies going some way towards incorporating a spatial dimension to their analyses. Historical geographies, such as those by Ghosh (2014) and Sharma (1978) for instance, have taken pains to reconstruct some semblance of the historical “space” within which the charters existed by attempting to locate the places and geographical units mentioned in the inscriptions on the ground. A limited number of studies have also considered the locational geography of the charters, and identified patterns in their distribution to provide insight into regional geopolitics and political alliances, the spread of land grants and Brahmanical institutions, and the development of agrarian economies over time (e.g. Singh 1994; Verma 1992).

Despite such examples, however, the archaeological realities of the regions in which they are situated have been largely ignored. With this being the case, all resulting conclusions regarding the wider societal and cultural settings in which the copperplates existed are thus, ultimately, still based primarily (if not solely) on readings of these and other textual sources. Nowhere in discussions of the practices mentioned in or reflected by the inscriptions is there an attempt to link or relate these practices and processes to the archaeological evidence for what was taking place on the ground. This is of considerable concern for two main reasons. First, without consideration of the physical realities of the various contexts in which the copperplates were produced and used we deprive ourselves of one large part of what the copperplates were and what they may have “meant” in their original contexts. Second, there is no escaping the fact that the copperplates (and all other contemporary inscriptions) are the products of an elite sector of society (the ruling powers who issued them) that were made for other elite groups (the recipients of land grants). With no consideration of their archaeological contexts, there is no way of knowing whether the picture of society that is recorded in these (elite) texts is representative of the wider social and cultural setting in which they existed. Nor is it possible to adequately and convincingly assess the societal impact of any of the practices and processes that the charters embody. When considered in this light, we are forced to accept that: on a theoretical level, many existing historical interpretations based on the texts of the copperplates and other documentary sources can only ever be hypothetical; and that on a methodological level, we need to consider the copperplates in terms of their contexts.

Unpicking this situation is complicated, not least because ultimately it stems from an even wider set of problems surrounding a general disjuncture between textual and archaeological approaches to the study of the past.³ Due to the fact that textual, archaeological, and (for that matter) art

historical studies have increasingly developed on their own disciplinary trajectories, each with their own sets of questions and ways of interrogating the evidence that they use, we should not necessarily expect textual scholars to engage expertly with archaeological material, or vice versa. That is not to say, however, that attempts to do so have not been made, and should not be encouraged. While not yet commonplace, there is already a clear awareness of the value of taking a more multi-disciplinary approach to the study of South Asia’s ancient past. Of particular interest as far as this paper is concerned, we might highlight a number of studies that have examined inscriptions in their archaeological and art historical contexts (e.g. Bakker 2002; Falk 2012; Hinüber & Skilling 2013; Neelis 2011; Skilling 2011; Willis 1996, 1997). That said, many approaches have so far only considered the more immediate context of the monuments upon which inscriptions are carved, or else they have focussed on earlier periods where the nature of both the inscriptions and available contextual evidence offers far more potential for such investigation.

It is in this connection that we encounter perhaps the most fundamental impediment to the archaeological contextualisation of the copperplates. For later historical periods—that is, from the early centuries C.E. onwards—we do not always have enough evidence at our disposal to provide this necessary context. Due to various historiographical factors surrounding the practice of archaeology in South Asia, the overwhelming majority of archaeological work has focussed on earlier periods (Hawkes 2014).⁴ This alone means that there simply is not the same quantity of archaeological material from, or materially derived understanding of, the fourth to seventh centuries when the copperplates were produced. Further, most archaeological investigations in South Asia have been targeted towards main urban centres, with little or no investigation of what were, in all likelihood, the most common types of settlement in antiquity: small towns and villages. As such, the evidence that we currently have at our disposal is not only a small sample of the total settlement archaeology of the subcontinent, but is also one that does not directly evidence rural settlement dynamics and the full spectrum of associated agricultural and economic dynamics that took place beyond the urban sphere (Hawkes 2014).

Of course, a number of studies have carried out more than single site excavations. Here, we might cite a recent and welcome movement towards archaeological surveys, and the incorporation of landscape perspectives in both archaeological and art historical research. This has not only meant that there has been increased awareness of hinterlands of urban settlements (e.g. Lal 1984; Erdosy 1988; Sinopoli and Morrison 2007; Smith 2001), but also attempts to integrate urban histories with wider agricultural and religious histories (e.g. Amar 2012; Casile 2014; Coningham et al. 2007; Shaw 2007). Yet, even these studies have tended to focus on earlier periods, and, when

considered in light of the number of single site excavations that take place, they are certainly not the norm.

Compounding matters, the way that many sites have been excavated limits our understanding of the evidence that *does* exist for the period in a number of ways (Hawkes 2014; Kennet 2004, 2013). It is not the intention here to rehearse what has been fully outlined and discussed elsewhere. But briefly, and at the risk of over generalisation, we can mention: (1) a tendency towards small-scale excavations, frequently with recourse to Wheeler's grid system, which limits our ability to say very much about the activities that took place "horizontally" across many settlements;⁵ (2) the common use of "vertical" methods of excavation that are not always sensitive to the complex depositional processes that can occur in later settlements;⁶ (3) connected with this, the somewhat crude definition of stratigraphic layers that frequently account for one or two centuries, which restricts our ability to identify changes in artefacts and activities over time; and (4) a widespread absence of systematic archaeobotanical and geoarchaeological sampling and analyses in standard excavations, which limits our understanding of almost every aspect of subsistence economies and environmental setting.

These factors are exacerbated by further issues surrounding the dating of deposits (or "layers") and sites from later periods. With scientific methods tending to be reserved for earlier periods, later historical layers are commonly dated on the basis of the artefacts that are found within them—usually with reference to four or five key pottery types. This is not, in itself a problem. Yet, because those layers often account for one or two centuries of occupation it is not possible to disentangle the rest of the pottery in each layer from each other, and so the majority of pottery tends to be subsumed into broad categories such as "coarse red ware" that exist across many centuries. This not only affects our understanding of the material itself—the basic building blocks of archaeological interpretation—but it also means we do not have sufficiently detailed understanding of artefacts from later periods to be able to use them to date excavated layers or sites found during survey with any more precision than broad centuries-long swathes of time.

All of this is not to detract from the undoubted value of the archaeological work that has been carried out. Rather, it is to be clear about the limitations of our current level of archaeological understanding for this particular period. Due to the problems outlined above, we are currently unable to date settlements from later historical periods with any precision, or, in the majority of cases, make detailed observations about the range of activities that took place at them or the environmental setting in which they existed. The absence of these basic building blocks of archaeological interpretation also constrains our ability to consider the evidence we have from a diachronic perspective, and potentially undermines our ability carry out new archaeological investigations. All of which, at least as far as

this study is concerned, limits the extent to which we can rely on the existing corpus of archaeological evidence to provide us with the necessary context for the study of the copperplates. This being the case, we are forced to admit that neither archaeologists nor textual scholars are well equipped to consider the copperplates in relation to their archaeological contexts.

From this review then, we can see that the study of the copperplate charters illustrates something of both the relationship between textual scholarship and archaeology, and the study of this particular data set presents its own problems. In essence, one of the main data sets that we have for the study of one entire period of South Asia's past—the charters—resemble a floating entity, ungrounded in space and time, with little conception of its archaeological or geographical contexts. Sadly, due to a variety of factors, we do not have sufficient grasp of these archaeological contexts to study in relation to the copperplates. Consequently, we have a limited understanding of the practices and processes reflected in and by the charters, and, by extension, the period in general.

Points of Departure

The issues inherent in the study of the copperplate charters that have been outlined here are not unrecognised. Indeed, acknowledging the limitations, recent research has attempted to invest the study of these inscriptions with more of an archaeological perspective. That is to say: engaging with them as material objects, that were themselves products of a particular practice, and thus representative of that practice; and at the same time, attempting to ground them in space and time, in order to shed light on the contexts in which they existed—both at the level of the contexts these charters were used, and the wider societal and cultural framework in which they existed.

Here, it is the proposition that we can begin to think about the original context of these inscriptions by considering their provenance that is of particular importance. Most reports of the discoveries of copperplate charters contain written accounts of where and how they were found. In some instances, they are recorded as having been found while already in the possession of another person, usually an inhabitant of a village, or a local metal smith. For example, the Yavatmal copperplates of Pravarasena II, which were "rescued from a coppersmith's melting pot" (Shastri 1997: 95). In these instances, it is, of course, impossible to ascertain their original find spot—their provenience has been lost. In other instances, however, the charters are recorded as having been unearthed from specific locations as was the case with the Mandhal copperplate of Rudrasena II (Shastri 1997: 85-88), which was found while ploughing in a field near the modern village settlement, or the Balaghat copperplate of Pravarasena II (Mirashi 1963: 69-72) found while digging the foundations of a new building. It may be that in these instances the find spots bear some relation to

the original context of the charters, specifically: of where the person, persons or institution to whom charter was issued kept or stored the charter.

Of course, any such identification can only be a (crude) estimate. A variety of factors may influence the life history of an object after it is made; and it is not possible to reconstruct this history based on the find spot of a charter alone. It must also be admitted that these objects, while not always small, were still portable and could have moved in any number of ways during their history. Nevertheless, given the perceived importance and value of these charters, it would be reasonable to assume that they would have been preserved safely—at least while the land grant, the subject of the charter, remained legally binding and the charter retained its primary meaning. We might also speculate that during this time, the charter may have been kept close to hand. It is also perfectly possible that the charters may have continued to be invoked to substantiate or legitimise subsequent claims centuries later; or that they retained some sort of value, though perhaps with a secondary meaning, long after the grants they recorded ceased to be valid.

There are one or two further observations that can be made of the accounts of their discoveries that allow us to entertain the idea that the provenience of these inscriptions may be related to their original contexts. In various instances across the subcontinent, copperplates have been found, undisturbed, in what appear to be primary deposits—carefully stored within large earthenware jars intentionally placed within ancient structures or buried.⁷ If we assume (and it is important to be clear, this will always be supposition) that these charters were deposited in this way while those who buried them retained some conception of their original meaning and importance, then it is not hard to imagine that the charters may have been deposited not long after their production and certainly during a time when their grants were considered relevant.⁸ In addition, we also know of a number of charters where the names of the villages granted in the inscriptions bear a remarkably close resemblance to the modern name of the place where they were found. For example, the copperplate charter that was found while digging in the village of Chamak in Maharashtra, records the grant of a village named “Charmanka” (Mirashi 1963: 22).

Grounding the Charters: Mapping

This being the proposition, research carried out by the British Museum’s “Politics, Ritual and Religion in Early India” project, supported by the Leverhulme Trust, compiled the published details of all known copperplate inscriptions dating to between the fourth and seventh centuries C.E. in South Asia.⁹ Special attention was paid to the accounts of the discoveries of the charters, and in each instance, an assessment was made as to whether that charter had been discovered in an “archaeological” context. By these means, it was found that over half of the charters (131

out of the total 243), had been unearthed or found in such a way as might suggest that they had been retrieved from a specific context or general location associated with their original use in antiquity. A further 22 are recorded, somewhat ambiguously, as having been found “in a village”. There is no way of knowing whether they were recovered while already in possession of an individual, or had been unearthed in that village. Of the 90 remaining charters, 82 are recorded as having been found in someone’s possession, with no details of where (or how) they were found originally. In fact, there are only eight copperplates for which we have little or no provenance, with their “find spots” being the places where they were first reported (usually a museum or government institution), after the charters themselves had already been transported from an unspecified location. Given the large number of charters involved, this represents a remarkably small percentage (3%) of “anonymous” copperplates, and so provides us with a relatively clear basis from which to proceed archaeologically. Thus, the geographical locations of the find spots of all of the charters with a recorded provenance—including both those with an “archaeological” provenience and those without—were then identified and mapped as part of the project (see Fig. 2).¹⁰

Thus mapped, all the details recorded by the copperplate charters are immediately and geographically grounded in space. This allows us to examine their spatial distribution, in conjunction with their texts, and identify patterns in the various practices and processes that they embody and represent. As straightforward as this process might seem, the recent nature of the mapping means that the resulting lines of enquiry have yet to be fully explored.¹¹ Nonetheless, consideration of the basic distribution of the find spots of the charters does enable us to make one or two preliminary observations.

First, and most immediately, if we group the charters according to the royal dynasties that issued them, we can see that they cluster in only five or six specific geographical areas (see Fig. 3). These are: the broad swathe of the Ganges Basin, which corresponds to the charters issued by the Guptas; parts of modern Gujarat, which correspond to the charters issued by the Maitrakas; Karnataka and parts of northern Kerala, corresponding to the charters issued by the Kadambas; the Vidarbha region of northeast Maharashtra, corresponding to the charters issued by the Vakatakas; parts of southeast Madhya Pradesh, Chattisgarh and northwest Odisha, corresponding to the charters issued by the Nalas, Panduvamshis and Sharabhapuris; and areas of the East coast of Andhra Pradesh, Odisha and West Bengal, corresponding to the charters issued by the early Pallavas, Vishnukundins and related dynasties. That the charters issued by different dynasties cluster together in these geographical areas suggests that even those that did not emerge from “archaeological” contexts may not have travelled far between being unearthed and being reported—at least, not on the scale of having been moved to different

states or regions. Of course, it is highly likely that additional copperplate charters will continue to be discovered in the future. Yet, given the way that these known charters are

distributed, it is unlikely that the locations of any hitherto undiscovered charts would significantly change this pattern.

Fig. 2: Map showing the locations of the find spots of copperplate charters dating to between the fourth and seventh centuries CE with identifiable provenience in South Asia

Fig. 3: Map showing the locations of the find spots of copperplate charters grouped by issuing dynasties

What is also striking about this distribution is that aside from the charters issued by the Gupta kings, the find spots of all other known copperplate charters issued between the fourth and seventh centuries C.E. are confined to relatively small localised areas. This has implications for how we conceive of the practice of land grants by royal charter during the “Gupta Era”. As noted, they have traditionally tended to be considered very much as pan-Indian phenomena, and discussed in terms of grand narratives that have sought to identify large-scale trends and developments occurring across the subcontinent (e.g. Sharma 2001). While their distribution demonstrates that copperplate charters were issued in various locations, and much as the practices that they embody were part of wider processes that seem to have extended across large parts of South Asia, the fact that they cluster tightly in the way they do suggests that the practice of land grants was limited to relatively small parts of the subcontinent and was not universal. In fact, the practice was limited to the areas that correspond to the core territories of the issuing dynasties. Large parts, if not the majority, of the subcontinent did not witness this practice at all. This “simple” result of “charting” the copperplates not only serves to underscore the necessity of improving our understanding of the archaeological contexts of both those areas in which the charters were issued and those where they were not, but also means that any further consideration of them has to be aware of the pitfalls involved in constructing grand narratives on the basis of the copperplate charters, and consider the practices reflected in them and their societal effects, at least in an immediate sense, as also being limited to the areas of their production and circulation.

In addition, it is now also possible to consider the distribution of these charters in relation to when they were produced. Archaeologically speaking, we are, admittedly, on somewhat shaky ground here—the charters may not have been deposited in the same locations as those that they bestowed and conferred. However, if we continue with our proposition that the find spots of these charters may loosely correspond to their original “use-areas”, when we group the charters not only by issuing dynasty but also by their issue-dates, we can reconstruct, in general terms, the spread of these charters and the practices relating to them in different parts of subcontinent over time (see Fig. 4). This reveals that the earliest copperplates were issued in the Ganges Basin and the Vidarbha region of central India, which corresponds to those issued by the Guptas—generally accepted as the dynasty that first conceived of this practice (Sharma 1958)—and their immediate neighbours, the Vakatakas and Valkhas. Later charters are located in geographically more distant regions.¹²

Studies of the texts of these charters in conjunction with other epigraphic evidence from across the subcontinent have resulted in a detailed political historical framework that informs what we know about most of the kings and families

who issued the charters. From this, we also know that the dynasties mentioned in the charters were related to each other through matrimonial or contractual political alliances (Kulke 2004). What is interesting in this connection is that the chronology of the geographical spread of these charters appears to correspond with that of these political alliances. There is not the space to go into this in detail here. The point is simply to highlight the fact that by geographically locating the charters we can see that the spread of the practice of charters corresponds to the spread of political alliances, related with which were concepts of kingship and support for Brahmins embodied in the adoption of the practice of land grants recorded in Sanskrit. Identifying the geographic locations of the archaeological contexts of the charters thus provides us with another framework in which to think about such issues and further explore these relationships.

Grounding the Charters: Exploring Archaeological Contexts

For all the undoubted benefits of locating the copperplate charters on the ground, the main benefit of doing so, at least from an archaeological perspective, is that once grounded, we have a space in which we can begin to explore their archaeological contexts. To this end, a pilot study was recently carried out to investigate the find spots of the charters in the Vidarbha region—just one of the regions where clusters of copperplate charters have been identified. As noted, the Vidarbha region was ruled by the eastern Vakataka dynasty, one of the first to have adopted the practice of granting land by royal charter, presumably as part of a wider process of political alliance and cultural rapprochement with the Gupta dynasty to the North.

The Vakatakas have been the subject of much textual and art historical research (see Bakker 1997, 2004; Shastri 1997), from which we are fortunate in having a good understanding of the political and religious framework of their kingdom. As far as the eastern Vakataka copperplate charters are concerned, the effects of this practice have traditionally been considered to demonstrate that the Vakatakas “civilised” or colonised parts of the Vidarbha region.¹³ With the eastern Vakatakas being understood to have migrated to this “peripheral” region from the “core” area of Western Vakatakas further to the southwest, their issuing of land grants has frequently been understood as part of a political and economic aim to settle new areas (see Kulke 2004). This is with reference to wider models that posit the spread of Brahmanical temple institutions, expansion of an agrarian economy and supposed settlement of new areas in relation to the granting of land and references to revenue derived from the farming of that land—concepts that are implicitly informed by wider debates about both the expansion of agriculture in Early Historic India, and a subsequent “feudal” phase of economy and society.

Fig. 4: Map showing the locations of the find spots of copperplate charters grouped by the date they were issued

However, in this region, like all the areas where copperplates were issued, the settlement dynamics of the region that could provide the necessary context to understand the practice of land grants and its effects have not been examined. That is not to say that archaeological investigations have never taken place in the region: a number of large and important settlements have been found, surveyed and excavated over the last few decades, including sites such as: Adam (*IAR 1988-89: 50-62; IAR 1990-91: 63-68; Nath 1992*), Kaundinyapur (Dikshit 1968; Mishra et al. 2016; Smith 2001), Mahurjhauri (Deo 1973; Mohanty 2002, 2003, 2006), and Pauni (Deo and Joshi 1972; Nath 1998). However, the extent to which we can draw on this archaeological information to better understand the wider context in which the charters existed is still largely hampered by the limitations inherent in the way the region has been approached archaeologically, and in the way that these sites have been excavated (as outlined above). For the most part, previous archaeological research has focussed on its early Iron Age, or “megalithic”, remains while ignoring later historical periods.¹⁴ Thankfully, this is beginning to change, with renewed scholarly interest in the historical

archaeology of the region (Sawant 2012), with recent landmark surveys of targeted areas around the known Vakataka centre of Ramtek (Lacey 2016), and with the recent excavation of Nagardhan, a site long supposed to have been a capital of the Vakatakas (Bakker 1997).¹⁵ Despite these recent and welcome advances, many questions still remain, particularly in relation to rural areas of the region, and we are far from being able to fully contextualise the copperplate charters.

With such caveats in mind, therefore, the provenance of the copperplate charters from this region (see Table 1), indicates that a reasonably high percentage of them were found through excavations at places that can be geographically identified. Of the 29 copperplates issued by the Vakatakas, 15 (or 51.7%) were found in the ground, with a further two (6.9%) recorded simply as having been found in the village where they were discovered, and five (17.2%) recorded as having been found in the possession of an individual (see Fig. 5). Seven were recorded only after they had already been displaced from their original context and transported from the region.

Fig. 5: Map showing the locations of the find spots of copperplates issued by the Vakatakas in Vidarbha (names of copperplate sites correspond to those in Table 1)

Preliminary reconnaissance, using extensive methods of informant-based village-to-village survey, was then carried out in and around the majority of the villages where copperplates had been found.¹⁶ In those areas where surveys were conducted, they revealed the locations of archaeological sites in the immediate vicinity of every single copperplate find spot, with a total of 53 sites being recorded. In the majority of instances (11 of the 15 copperplate sites that were surveyed), settlement sites were identified at either the same precise location where copperplate charters had been unearthed, or in the same village where they were found.¹⁷ In the remaining four instances, settlements were noted within only one or two kilometres of the find spots of the charters.¹⁸ On a procedural level, this lends weight to the proposition that we can use the find spots of the charters as an indicator for their original context. The sites that were encountered during survey all date from the early Iron Age to the late early

historical period (i.e. contemporary to the Vakatakas), and beyond. While a number of these sites were already known—for example, the excavated sites at Mahurjhauri (Deo 1973; Mohanty 2002, 2003), Mansar (Wellstead 1834; Joshi & Sharma 2000), Mandhal (*IAR 1969-70*: 20; *IAR 1970-71*: 24; *IAR 1975-76*: 36; *IAR 1976-77*: 39), and Pauni (Deo & Joshi 1972; Nath 1998)—in many cases, the connection between these sites at the find spots of the copperplate charters had not previously been made explicit. In addition, 29 of the sites encountered during this reconnaissance represent new discoveries. This process has thus provided us with clear and additional contextual information, located archaeologically, corroborating some of the assumptions made textually, while also providing further data for future consideration of this important set of objects. Preliminary observations of these sites are provided in Table 2, and their locations in relation to the find spots of the copperplate charters are illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Map showing the locations of archaeological sites associated with the find spots of Vakataka copperplate charters in Vidarbha (site codes correspond to those in Table 2)

Table 1. Details of the copperplate charters issued by the eastern Vakatakas in Vidarbha

Name	Provenience	Description	References
Balaghat (district) copper plates	Displaced and transported	The Balaghat copper plates of Prothivisena II were discovered somewhere in the Balaghat district prior to May 1893, when the plates were sent to the Asiatic Society of Bengal by the Deputy Commissioner of Balaghat. According to reports that accompanied their deposit with the Asiatic Society, the plates were discovered "some time ago, hanging to a tree in the jungle". The charter consists of five plates, but only three bear inscriptions and the attached seal is also without inscription indicating that the charter was unfinished. Mirashi also states that the charter was left incomplete, as it does not specify the charters donation. It does however record the planned place of issue, Prothivisena II's temporary residence at Vembāra, which Mirashi has identified with the modern village of Bambal, 28 mile east of Chandrapur and 2 miles west of the Wainganga river. Although incomplete, the importance of the inscription lies in its mention of Prothivisena II and his father Narendrasena II. Prior to the discovery of this charter, neither ruler was known as only grants of Pravarasena II were known before 1893. Because of this, the description of both Narendrasena II, Pravarasena II's son (?) and Prothivisena II were new contributions to the known Vakataka history.	Kielhorn, 1908: 267; Mirashi, 1963: 79-80; Shastri, 1997: 70-79
Balaghat copper plate of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	Balaghat has been identified as being the original discovery location of the copper plate inscription now housed in the Patna Museum. The plate was discovered during the excavations for the foundations of the new District Superintendent of Police's bungalow in the town in 1919. The inscription, of which only one plate is now known, records the donation of the village of Sriparnaka by Pravarasena II to three beneficiaries: Gangariya, Vasuraya and Rudraya. The charter was issued to replace an earlier grant of the village Manapallika. The donation was made to augment the religious merit of Pravarasena II's mother, Prabhavati Gupta, indicating that she was alive at the time of issue. However, as only one of the plates of this grant is known, the date and place of issue is not known.	Mirashi, 1963: 69-72; Shastri, 1997: 35-36
Belora Copper plate of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	This set of four copper plates was discovered in the village of Belora. Mirashi believed that the plates were from two different sets of charters, whilst Shastri argues that the charter was originally three plates long but one of the plates was considered to be defective and so a new plate was created - however, the defective plate was never disposed of and additional plates were added to create a fake charter. According to Shastri this forgery took place at the time the charter was created and possibly had official "collusion" in its creation. The charter, dating to the 11th year of Pravarasena II reign, records the donation of the village Mahallalata to Suryasvamin.	Mirashi, 1963: 16-21; Shastri, 1997: 15
Bidar copper plate inscription of Devasena (found out of context)	Displaced and transported	The location of the original five copper plates and their ring are no longer known, but iron reproductions of the plates were created by a bidri worker in Bidar when the plates were brought to him by a villager from the Bechchali taluk of the Bidar district. Although the original plates are untraceable, the iron copies provide a record of Devasena's donation of the village of Velpakonda in "favour of one Raddochha, a scholar of the four Vedas". The inscription was issued from Vatsagulma. According to Shastri, this is the only known complete official grant of Devasena. Shastri also argues that this plate is important because it may prove that the Vatsagulma branch of the Vakatakas spread into Karnataka, as the ending of the named village in the inscription may suggest.	Shastri, 1997: 108-110
Chamak copper plate of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	This copper plate charter of Pravarasena II was discovered in 1868 during the ploughing of a field at the village of Chamak. Chamak, in ancient times known as Charmanka, is located four miles south west of Illichpur; (Ellichpur or Illychpur), the old name for Achalpur. The inscription, incised on seven plates and with an attached seal, records the donation of the village of Charmanka by Pravarasena II at the request of Kondaraja. The donation was given to 1,000 Brahmanas of various sects and schools, and the charter lists 49 of these donees by name. The charter was issued in the 18th year of Pravarasena II reign. The charter is now in the collection of the British Library (Oriental Manuscript shelfmark: Ind. Ch. no. 16). Wikipedia page (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chamak_copper_plates)	Mirashi, 1963: 22-27; Shastri, 1997: 16-18.
Dudia Copper plate inscription of Pravarasena II	Displaced	This charter, which consists of four copper plates, three of which are inscribed and one, which is blank, was discovered in the possession of some Gonds in the village of Dudia. The charter records the donation of 25 bhumis (nivartanas) in the village of Darbbhamalaka to Yaksharya and 60 bhumis of land in the village of Karmakara-grama to Kalisharman. The land was donated in the 23rd year of Pravarasena II reign.	Mirashi, 1963: 43; Shastri, 1997: 24
India Office Copper plate inscription of Devasena	Displaced and transported	This single plate of a charter issued by Devasena is part of the India Office collection but its origins are not known. It is not known where the plate was discovered or how it came to be part of the India Office Collections or if the rest of the charter still exists. According to the single plate of the charter, it was issued at Vatsagulma and starts immediately by citing Devasena's order of the grant. The inscription records the donation of a village (unidentified) to two Brahmanas Dharmasvamin and Bhavasvamin of the shandilya gotra. According to Shastri the exact location of the donated land is not known but may possibly be in the Akola district.	Shastri, 1997: 40-41

Name	Provenience	Description	References
Indore copper plate of Pravarasena II	Displaced and transported	The Indore copper plates of Pravarasena II were found in the possession of Pandit Vamanshastri Islampurkar of Indore, although the plates do not originate from Indore. It is possible, according to Mirashi and Shastri, that the plates originate somewhere in the Balaghat district. The charter is interesting for a number of reasons: first, there are numerous mistakes in the engraving; and second, it appears that the charter is merely formalising an earlier grant, perhaps to Vishakarya and confirming the donation to his son and grandsons. The first plate of this charter was not originally found with the following three, but was discovered in the collection of Dr Nagoo of Indore.	Mirashi, 1963: 40; Shastri, 1997: 24-25
Jamb copper plates of Pravarasena II	Displaced	The Jamb copper-plates were discovered in 1940 in the possession of an individual named Baburaro Madhavrao Athole in Jamb, about 7 miles north by east of Hinganghat. The charter records the donation by Pravarasena II to a Brahmachārin called Kalakutta. The charter donates the village of Kothuraka to Kalakutta. The charter was issued in the 2nd year of Pravarasena II reign. Mirashi identifies the donated village of Kothuraka with the site now occupied by Mangaon (2.5 miles north by west, on the right bank of the Wunna), although Shastri states the village cannot be identified.	Mirashi, 1963: 10; Shastri, 1997: 11-13
Mahurzari/Mahurjhari copper plates of Prithivisena II	Archaeological	This set of 5 copper plates dating to the reign of Prithivisena II, were discovered in June 1971 in a field during ploughing. The field was owned by Shri Borkar who at that time, lived in the village. The village is an ancient site with many archaeological remains dating to the Vakataka period. There are also stone circles which date as far back as 3000 years suggesting continued habitation throughout this period. This is one of the only known copper plate charters of Prithivisena II which is complete. The charter was issued in the king's 17th year of rule and records the grant of the village Jamalakhetaka to the Brahmanas Vishṇudatta and Bhavadatta, residents of Prithivipura, where the charter was issued from. This copper plate charter is now housed in the Central Museum, Nagpur.	Kolte, 1972: 183-198; Shastri, 1997: 103
Mandhal copper plate charter of Prithivisena II, year 10	Archaeological	This set of five copper plates were discovered during archaeological excavations undertaken at Mandhal by Nagpur University. These plates were discovered with two other Vakataka copper plate charters. Each charter was complete with ring and seal attached. The copper plate charter, inscribed on four plates, records the donation of the village Govasahika to four Brahmanas, two, Maheshvarasvamin and Brahmasvamin, are also mentioned in the Mandhal copper plate charter of Prithivisena II, year 2. Shastri argues that the three plates found at this site record donations by two Vakataka kings to two generations of the same family.	Shastri, 1997: 99-103
Mandhal copper plate charter of Prithivisena II, year 2	Archaeological	The charter consists of four plates, which were found in an earthen vessel during excavations, along with two other Vakataka copper plate inscriptions. The charter was issued in the second year of Prithivisena II reign and was found complete with ring and seal - providing the earliest known complete example of a copper plate charter from the reign of Prithivisena II. The charter records the donation of the village Kurubhajjaka by its chief to three brothers, Maheshvarasvamin, Agnisvamin and Brahmasvamin, sons of Matrisvamin. Two of these brothers are also the benefactors of the Māṇḍhaḷ copper plate of Prithivisena II and Matrisvamin was the donee of the Mandhal copper plate of Pravarasena II.	Shastri, 1997: 97-99
Mandhal copper plate inscription of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	This set of five copper plates were discovered during archaeological excavations undertaken at Mandhal by Nagpur University. These plates were discovered with two other later Vakataka copper plate charters. Each charter was complete with ring and seal attached. This charter was issued from Pravarapura and it records the donation of the village Mayasagrama in favour of Upadhyaya Matrisvamin by Pravarasena II. The charter dates to the 16th and 17th year of Pravarasena II reign, with the first date recording the year when the donation was made and the second year recording when the charter was written and issued. According to the inscription one third of the religious merit of the donation is to go to Ajnakabhatarika, mother of Narendraraja, although it is not known who these two people are. According to Shastri, the identification of Mayasagrama is not possible at present, but it is also not possible to rule out Mandhal as the possible location of the ancient village.	Shastri, 1997: 88-90
Mandhal copper plate of Rudrasena II	Archaeological	This set of four copper plates was discovered during the ploughing of a field in the village of Mandhal in 1982. The plates, which date to the 5th year of Rudrasena II reign, record the donation of four villages, Selludraha, Achchhabhallika, Suragramaka and Aragramaka, which were used as a Brahmana settlement, occupied by various Brahmanas from different sects. The charter was written by Senapati Vibhishana for Rudrasena II, and is stated to have been issued by the King himself following a command from a form of Vishnu.	Shastri, 1997: 85-88
Mansar copper plate	Archaeological	Shastri refers to this plate as the Mansar plate, whilst Mirashi refers to the plate as the Ramtek plate. The plate, the fourth of a five plate charter, was discovered whilst digging for manganese on the outskirts of Mansar. It is not known where the donated areas are or where the plate was issued. According to Shastri, Mirashi believes that the plate dates to the time of	Mirashi, 1963: 73-75; Shastri, 1997: 36-37

Name	Provenience	Description	References
		Pravarasena II due to similarities with known charters of this time, but Shastri argues that these similarities can also be seen in other charters of different rulers and so cannot be considered to be certain.	
Masod Copper plate inscription of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	This charter, issued in the 19th year of Pravarasena II reign, records the donation of a piece of land in the north west of Matsakadraha village in honour of 19 Brahmanas who are named in the inscription. The set of five plates were discovered in a field at Masod whilst it was being ploughed. The plates are now part of the collection of the Central Museum, Nagpur.	Shastri and Gupta, 1981: 108-116
Miregaon copper plate of Prabhavati Gupta	Archaeological	The set of five copper plates were found when a field was being dug near the village of Miregaon. The inscription records the donation of the village Jalapura-vataka to support a group of Brahmanas by Prabhavati Gupta in the 20th year of her son, Pravarasena II reign. The contents of the plates are the same as the Riddhapur plates except for the details of donations. The plate was drafted by a minister named Chandra.	Shastri, 1997: 91-93
Mohalla copper plate of Prithivisena I (?)	Uncertain	This plate, which is unfinished, was found in the village of Mohalla in the Durg district of Chattisgarh. The details of the charter are not recorded in the inscription as it is not finished. According to Shastri the plate is possibly dated to the reign of Prithivisena I. Mirashi refers to this plate as the Durg plate. It is now part of the collection of the Central Museum, Nagpur.	Mirashi, 1963: 76-78; Shastri, 1997: 6
Pattan copper plate charter of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	The five copper plates that make up this charter were found in a field during ploughing in the village of Pattan in 1935. The charter was issued by Pravarasena II in the 27th year of his reign and is, according to Shastri, a unique charter in the Vakataka examples because it provides for a free feeding house, attached to a temple as opposed to an individual donation of a land grant. The donation was made at the request of Narayanaraja.	Shastri, 1997: 31
Pauni copper plate of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	The set of four copper plates was discovered by Shri Ramchandra Narayan Wakadiker whilst digging in the ramparts of Pauni. The charter was issued from Pravaraपुरa and records the donation of land measuring 50 nivarttanans by royal measure to Dugarya, a student of the Rigveda and part of the Aupamanyava gotra. According to the inscription the land is located in the 'holy place of Achalapuka' and was given in exchange for another plot of land. The grant was issued in the 32nd year of Pravarasena II's reign.	Kolte, 1969: 53-57.
Pune copper plates of Prabhavati Gupta	Displaced and transported	The Pune copper-plates of Prabhavati Gupta were discovered in the possession of Balwant Bhau Nagarkar, a copper smith from Ahmadnagar, Maharashtra. According to Mirashi, the plates had been preserved as a family heirloom for several generations. The two recovered plates of the charter record the donation of the village Danguna (or Inguna) to Chanalasvamin by Prabhavati Gupta during the 13th year of her reign as regent for her minor son. The donated village in the copper plate has been located in the modern village of Hinganghat in Wardha district. The charter was issued from Nandivardhana, the modern Nagardhan near Ramtek.	Mirashi, 1963: 5-6; Shastri, 1997: 9-11
Riddhapur copper plates of Prabhavati Gupta	Displaced	The Riddhapur copper plates were found in the possession of Mahanta Dattaraja of the Mahanubhava sect in the town of Riddhapur. Four plates were discovered, the first and fourth are only inscribed on the inner surface whilst the second and third plates are inscribed on both sides. The charter records the donation of a field 'only for enjoyment', a farmhouse and four residences of ploughmen in the administrative division of Koshika. The donation was made to the Brahmanas of the Taittiriya shakha of the Black Yajurveda and Parashara gotra by Prabhavati Gupta in the 19th year of Pravarasena II's reign. The charter includes reference to Prabhavati Gupta's Gupta lineage alongside that of her Vakataka heritage. The charter also includes a reference to Prabhavati Gupta's two sons, both of whom were kings (Damodarasena and Pravarasena II).	Shastri, 1997: 21-23.
Siwani Copper plate charter of Pravarasena II	Displaced	The copper plate, which dates to year 18 of Pravarasena II reign, was found in the possession of Hazari Gond Malguzar, resident of Pindarai village, in 1836. The charter records the donation of the village Brahmapuraka. The name of the donated village, together with the names of the surrounding locations mentioned in the charter have led to the suggestion that the charter was originally from the Gondia region of the Bhandara district. The plate is referred to as the Siwani (Seoni) plate as this is the main town in the district, and as the original find spot of the inscription is not known. This location point is possibly incorrect - there are numerous villages called Pindarai in this region, which could also be the discovery place of this charter.	Fleet, 1888: 243; Shastri, 1997: 19
Thalner copper plate of Harisena	Displaced and transported	The Thalner copper plates, which consist of three inscribed copper plates with a ring, were acquired from a resident of Thalner by a blacksmith from Dhule. The plates date to the third year of Harisena's reign and are the only known official charter of the king, who was the last ruler of the Vatsagulma branch of the Vakatakas. The plates record the donation of two villages and some land to a group of Brahmanas who were students of Samaveda.	Shastri, 1997: 111

Name	Provenience	Description	References
Tigaon copper plates of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	The Tigaon copper plates of Pravarasena II were discovered in this village in 1942 when the house of Kadu Patil was demolished to make way for the Itarsi-Nagpur Central Railway line. Mirashi refers to the plates as the Pandhurna plates even though they were found in the village of Tigaon. There are five copper plates, which record the donation of 2000 nivartanas of land by royal measure in the village of Dhuvavataka (Dhruvavataka) to a number of Brahmanas. An additional 26 nivartanas in two other villages is recorded in the third plate as being specifically donated to the Brahmana Somarya. Both Mirashi and Shastri argue that this third plate is actually a forgery, inserted into the charter at a later date to benefit Somarya. The first part of the donation, of the 2000 nivartanas was issued in exchange for the earlier donation by Prithivisena I of the village of Vijayavalli-vataka. The charter was issued in the 29th year of Pravarasena II reign and was issued from the temple of Pravaresvara.	Mirashi, 1963: 63; Shastri, 1997: 32-33
Tirodi copper plate of Pravarasena II	Archaeological	The four Tirodi copper plates were discovered in manganese mines at Tirodi in the 1930's. The copper plates date to year 23 of Pravarasena II and record the donation to Varunarya, a resident of Chandrapura, of the village Kosambakhanda in order to gain religious merit for both Pravarasena II and his mother Prabhavati Gupta. According to Mirashi the charter was written following the direct order of Pravarasena II. Wikipedia page (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tirodi_copper_plates).	Mirashi, 1938: 48-52.
Wadgaon Copper plate inscription of Pravarasena II	Displaced and transported	The exact location of this copper plate's discovery is not currently known. According to Mirashi the plates were brought to Dr S. S. Patwardhan at the Central Museum, Nagpur by Bhagwan Shiva Ganar of Yenur a village in the Hinganghat district. He had received the charter from his grandfather who lived in Wadgaon village, in the Warora tehsil in Chandrapur district. The inscription records the donation of four hundred nivartanas in the village of Velusuka to the Brahmana Rudrarya, in the 25th year of Pravarasena II.	Mirashi, 1963: 53; Shastri, 1997: 29-30.
Washim copper plates of Vindhyashakti II	Uncertain	The four copper plates were discovered by Pandit Vasudev Shastri Dhanagare in the town of Washim, which stands on the site of the ancient town of Vatsagulma. The plates are from the Vatsagulma branch of the Vakatakas and were produced for Vindhyashakti II in the 37th year of his reign. The charter records the donation of the village Akasapadda to fourteen Brahmanas by Vindhyashakti II. The charter records the names of the Brahmanas and the share of the village, which they were given. According to Shastri the charter is important in that it proves that Pravarasena I, who ruled as part of the undivided family, had at least four sons who all became kings, which until the discovery of this charter had not been satisfactorily proven.	Mirashi, 1963: 93-100; Shastri, 1997: 37-40.
Yavatmal/Yawatmal copper plate inscription of Pravarasena II	Displaced	Two copper plates of this charter were rescued from a coppersmith's melting pot in Yavatmal by R. M. Saklecha. Saklecha acquired them for Prashant P. Kulkarni. According to Shastri, when compared to other Vakataka inscriptions it is possible to argue that the plates recovered represent the second and last plates of a charter. The charter is dated to the 26th year of Pravarasena II reign and records the renewal of a donation of an area of land and two house sites in the village of Latakapalli to Indrariya and Svamideva. That this charter records a renewal of a previously granted donation makes the Yavatmal copper plates very unusual in the corpus of known Vakataka inscriptions. The inscription was written by Bappadeva, who is also mentioned in the Siwani and Wadgaon Vakataka inscriptions.	Shastri, 1997: 95-96

Table 2. Details of the archaeological sites identified during survey of the find spots of the copperplate charters in Vidarbha

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Adam	ADM01	Adam	20.997756	79.453906	Settlement	Fortification, habitation mound, surface scatter	The site is characterised by a pronounced habitation mound, approx. 250x300m, surrounded by an earth and stone built rampart and moat. Surface remains are visible in low frequencies across the surface of the site.	Mid-1 st millennium B.C.E. to mid-1 st millennium C.E. (Iron Age to Vakataka)	Nath 1992
Arambha	ARB01	Arambha	20.560000	78.977250	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	Arambha is a well-known archaeological site excavated by ASI. The western part of the village bears thick habitation deposits.	1st millennium B.C.E. to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Iron Age to Vakataka)	IAR 1991-92: 73-74

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Bellura Chandurbazar	BLC01.I	Bellura	21.197000	77.790360	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The old settlement was located in the central part of the village, which is owned by Deshmukh family. There is a small garhi, now in ruins, which was built by the ancestors of Deshmuk. Some potsherds of Early Historic period were collected from this garhi.	Late centuries B.C.E.to early centuries C.E. (Early Historic)	None. New Discovery
Bellura Chandurbazar	BLC01.II	Bellura	21.199720	77.792190	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	On the Northern part of the village along the west of road connecting Bellura from Rithpur (Riddhpur) potsherds were noticed on a large plot of land. This land is fenced and marked by a large old Tamarind. Pottery collection was made from this plot.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Bellora Loni	BLL01	Bellora	21.355420	78.207220	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The habitation soil is limited to the central part of the village, which is locally known as Garhi. The expanse of habitation soil is not more than two acres. Today an overhead water tank and a Panchayat office along with some village houses stands above this deposit. The deposit is not so prominent and preserves some pottery and brickbats. A small collection of pottery belonging to the Early Historic and Vakataka periods was collected from this place.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Early Historic and Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Brahmanwada	BMW01	Brahmanwada	21.257030	79.017860	Settlement	Habitation mound	A small mound located near the Maruti temple preserves Vakataka deposit. This is located about half a km east of the village. The extent of this mound is about 4 acres and thickness of the deposit is approx. 1m (as identified in visible sections).	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Deccan College. Unpublished
Garhi	CHD01.I	Chachondi	21.18566	77.47191	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The site is defined by a habitation mound and visible archaeological material on the surface of a large area of raised land. The habitation mound itself appears to be approximately 180m x 180m, based on discernable changes in elevation from the surrounding topography. Surface remains are visible on the surface of wide areas in every direction. Scatters extend for another 100m to the West, North and East. While to the South and southwest, they extend for approximately 150m.	Early cents C.E.to late-2nd millennium (late Early Historic to Early Modern)	None. New Discovery

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Chahagarh	CHD01.II	Chachondi	21.18929	77.47259	Settlement	Habitation mound, exposed sections, surface scatter	The site is defined by a habitation mound and visible archaeological material on the surface of a large area of raised land. The habitation mound itself appears to be approximately 160m x 160m. Its precise extent is difficult to ascertain without excavation, but archaeological remains visible in natural sections cease to occur beyond this extent. Scatters or archaeological material visible on the surface extend for another 50-100m to the North, East, South and southwest. The land immediately to the West drops suddenly to the river below.	1st millennium B.C.E.to early centuries C.E. (Iron Age to Early Historic)	None. New Discovery
Chachondi	CHD01.III	Chachondi	21.18975	77.46871	Settlement	Surface scatter	A scatter or surface material on cultivated land defines the site. Surface scatter extends for approximately 100m N-S x 75m E-W. At the time of survey, the land had recently been ploughed, so visibility was good. The density of surface material was low (max. 5 per square metre). The site was interpreted as a settlement. Its relation to the seemingly much larger nearby settlements at Garhi and Chahagarh is uncertain. It may have been a smaller secondary settlement, or indicate a separate phase of occupation of the wider site.	1st millennium B.C.E.to early centuries CE, and 2nd millennium (Iron Age to Early Historic, and medieval to Modern)	None. New Discovery
Chandankheda Mound	CND01	Chandankheda	20.261810	79.218740	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter, fortification, moat	Chandandankheda, which is a fortified settlement with a moat, is covered by present-day settlement. A thick habitation deposit is visible near the old medieval fortress, which also houses a medieval temple.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Early Historic and Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Deurwada medieval temple	DWD01.III	Deurwada	20.102650	79.059890	Religious (Temple)	Structural feature	In the central part of the Village a Shiva temple with many medieval sculptures were noticed.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Early Historic and Vakataka)	Sali 1998:17
Fokatpura	FKT01	Fokatpura	20.098720	77.127890	Settlement	Surface scatter	The nature of deposit suggests that the site is a single culture site and possibly was occupied for a very short duration. Lots of brickbats and sculptures recovered during excavations are seen at the site.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Jamb	JAM01	Jamb	20.613970	78.926190	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The habitation deposit of Jamb is quite extensive. The concentration of habitation mound is seen on the western side of the Samudrapur-Hinganghat highway. The entire village is settled on this deposit. The limits of the ancient habitation deposit exceed the village boundaries in the north and in the west and this patch are used to cultivate different varieties of crops. The area of this deposit is approx. (500m x 500m). A small water tank is located approx. one km northwest of the village.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Kharparia	KPR01	Kharparia	21.678890	79.697580	Spot find (Sati stone)	Sculpture	A sati memorial is present in the village.	Mid-2nd millennium C.E. (medieval)	None. New Discovery
Dongar Mahadev (Korambhi Caves A)	KRM01.I	Korambhi	20.833450	79.604140	Religious (Cave)	Rock cut cave	KRM01.I (locally known as Dongar Mahadev) is well connected with Pauni by an ancient track. This is a single rock cut cave, which is modified recently. The cave is devoid of any decorative carving, yet is similar in terms of its dimensions and architectural style to other examples elsewhere in the region that can be dated to the Early Historic period.	Late centuries B.C.E.to early centuries C.E. (Early Historic)	None. New Discovery
Korambhi Caves B and C	KRM01.II	Korambhi	20.830220	79.601440	Religious (Cave)	Rock cut cave	A small complex of two rock cut caves. The caves are devoid of any decorative carving, yet are similar in terms of its dimensions and architectural style to other examples elsewhere in the region that can be dated to the Early Historic period.	Late centuries B.C.E.to early centuries C.E. (Early Historic)	None. New Discovery
Katangdgara Ki Mashan Bhoomi	KTN01	Sasara and Katangdhara	20.980080	79.949780	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The habitation deposit at Katangdhara ki Mashan is about 2.5m thick and mainly contains early Historical habitation with some Vakataka deposits. The habitation mound and associated surface scatter extent over at least five acres. At present, the site is used as a cremation ground by the villages of Sasara and Katangdhara.	1st millennium B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Iron Age to Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Lal Deur	LLD01	Washim Town	20.093220	77.140860	Settlement	Habitation mound, structural feature, surface scatter	The mound was excavated by DMAMS. At present a Kshetrapal temple stands at this mound. The deposit is not more than a meter thick. A wall was exposed at the site.	Mid-1st millennium C.E.to mid-2nd millennium (Vakataka to medieval)	Sali, 1998

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Malli	MAL01	Malli	20.857770	79.502530	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	Large Iron Age habitation site excavated by Virag Sontanke of MSAD.	1st millennium C.E. (Iron Age)	None. New Discovery
Mahurjhari	MHR01	Mahurjhari	21.227980	79.006520	Settlement	Habitation mound, megalithic burials	This village is well-known for its Megalithic burials as well as the site of an early Iron Age and Early Historic settlement. The settlement preserves Early Historic and Vakataka deposits, which were excavated by Deccan College. Currently, open cast mining is destroying the site and its wider environs.	1st millennium B.C.E. to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Iron Age to Vakataka)	IAR 2003-04 (in press)
Bholahudki	MND01.I	Mandhal	20.941170	79.464670	Religious (Temple)	Structural feature	Ancient brick structure of Shiv temple of Vakataka period preserved on hill. It was excavated by Maharashtra State Department of Archaeology.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998
Temple near the Mosque	MND01.II	Mandhal	20.945920	79.464920	Religious (Temple)	Structural feature	The entire area is elevated with a sizeable amount of brickbats and brick courses visible on the surface. Presently, a Muslim graveyard and a mosque can be seen above this mound.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998
Shiv Temple near the Hindu graveyard	MND01.III	Mandhal	20.949190	79.462250	Religious (Temple)	Structural feature	This area belongs to Panchayat and is used as a burial ground. The remains of a Vakataka brick temple are visible in an exposure next to the road. This area is dotted with various large trees. This temple structure was exposed by the Maharashtra State Department.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998
Maruti Temple	MND01.IV	Mandhal	20.954150	79.457890	Spot find (Displaced sculptural)	Sculptural remains	Ganesha image, carved on sandstone and recently found in this tank, is currently lying next to the temple wall.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998
Mausoleum	MND01.V	Mandhal	20.949190	79.462250	Fort	Structural feature	The Mausoleum of Muslim saint Syed Faqrudin Hussaini is located next to the Primary School. This area was part of a medieval garhi. All these structures and the village are located on top of an earlier habitation mound (MND01.VII). The area is littered with pottery.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998
Mound near Rashtriya Vidyalaya	MND01.VI	Mandhal	20.955170	79.457640	Settlement	Surface scatter	The area preserves ancient habitation, which was excavated by MSAD.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998
Village Mandhal	MND01.VII	Mandhal	20.952870	79.460450	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The northwest side of the village adjacent to the primary school is located on the habitation deposit. This deposit is more than 2m thick. About 200 meters south of primary school a medieval temple with lots of sculptural remains was noted.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Meeregaon	MRG01.I	Meeregaon	20.998420	79.937970	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	The copper palate was found from the habitation deposit, which is actually an agricultural field of Mr Ganesh Jawanjar. Lots of pottery belonging to Vakataka period is seen at this place. The deposit is superficial and no mound like deposit is present in the village.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Meeregaon Sculpture	MRG01.II	Meeregaon	20.997280	79.937690	Spot find (Displaced sculptural)	Sculptural remains	The habitation deposit at Meeregaon covers at least half of the village. In the year 2008, while digging the foundations for construction of a new house Mr Ravindra Shavan Sathavane found a female figure on sandstone. Artistically and stylistically this figure belongs to the Vakataka Period. Pottery is present in the area from where this statue was unearthed.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Masod Cave	MSD01.I	Masod	21.090970	78.618530	Religious (Cave)	Rock cut cave	The Ramgarh cave (MSD01) is a rock cut cave carved in a porous and soft lateritic hill. The copper plate was discovered in an area lying between two hills. The cave is domical in shape from inside with 17.50m length x 4.30 m width and 4 m height. Lots of modern graffiti is seen inscribed on the wall of this cave. The face (entrance which was quite narrow originally) of the cave faces due east towards other hill which is located hardly one hundred meters east of this cave. The cave does not have any carvings or sculpture; however a narrow passage (about 15-20 feet deep) is located inside this cave.	Unidentified	None. New Discovery
Masod (Habitation)	MSD01.II	Masod	21.076510	78.621800	Settlement	Habitation mound, surface scatter	The habitation deposit of Masod is concentrated on the southern part of the village that houses a Primary Zilla Parishad school. This habitation deposit covers an area of about 4-5 acres. The thickness of this mound is about 2 to 2.5 meters. The mound is partly covered by the present day settlement and remaining part is under cultivation.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Mansar Palace	MSN01	Mansar	21.396316	79.278133	Palace	Structural features, surface scatter	Large brick built structural complex, recently excavated and misidentified as a Buddhist stupa. Surface remains visible over a wide area surrounding the palace structure.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Wellstead, 1934; IAR 1989-90: 127; Joshi & Sharma 1992
Hidimba Tekri	MSN02	Mansar	21.395637	79.273557	Religious (Temple)	Structural features, surface scatter	Complex of four temple shrines on the slope and summit of the hill, Hidimba Tekri, overlooking the palace.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Joshi & Sharma 1992; Baker 2008: 61

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Nagardhan / Hamlapuri	NGD01	Nagardhan	21.336576	79.314346	Settlement	Habitation mound, exposed sections, surface scatter	Multiple areas of habitation deposits and surface scatters of archaeological material located throughout and surrounding Nagardhan village, and extending as far as the nearby village of Hamlapuri. Initial impressions suggest that this may have been one very large settlement, or conglomeration of areas of occupation.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-2nd millennium C.E. (Early Historic to medieval)	Lacey, 2016
Nagardhan Fort	NGD02	Nagardhan	21.336936	79.315719	Fort	Structural features	Late medieval fort built on top of earlier habitation mound.	2nd millennium C.E. (medieval)	Unpublished
Padri	PDR01	Chamak	21.21223	77.46332	Settlement	Surface scatter	The site is defined by visible archaeological material on the surface. Surface scatter extends over an area approximately 300m N-S by 200m E-W. The entire area is cultivated, with the majority of the area being used as a plantation, making ground visibility extremely poor. Only the most northern and northeastern extents of the area defined by the surface scatter are used for other agricultural crops. At the time of survey, these fields were freshly ploughed, making visibility extremely good. Artefacts visible on the surface included pottery, terracotta beads, animal bone, brick, and worked stone (quern). Local villagers also testified to having found an urn filled with 64 silver coins and 5 gold coins while digging in this area the previous year.	Early centuries C.E.to mid-2nd millennium (late Early Historic to medieval)	None. New Discovery
Pachkhedi	PKD01	Pachkhedi	20.950970	79.502080	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	The habitation mound, excavated by ASI, is located about 200m West of the village and is locally known as Nadobaji (which is a mother Goddess temple). The highest part of the mound has a sati memorial. The main mound is about half an acre whereas the surface scatter extended for 3-4 acres.	1st millennium B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Iron Age to Vakataka)	IAR 1991-92
Pauni	PNI01.I	Pauni	20.791452	79.637855	Settlement	Fortifications, habitation mounds, surface scatters	An extensive habitation mound, together with brick built ramparts and a moat defines the site. The modern town of Pauni obscures most of the surface of the site. Yet, exposed sections and surface material is still visible at numerous locations within the fortification wall.	1st millennium B.C.E.to present (Iron Age to modern)	Deo & Joshi, 1972; Nath, 1998

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Jagannath Tekdi	PNI01.II	Pauni	20.78365	79.635730	Religious (Stupa)	Structural feature, surface scatter	Stupa site located about 2km on the south-eastern part of Pauni. Pottery was recovered from the southern, western and eastern areas near the hillock, while on the northern fringe the moat is located. Along with pottery, in the embankments of the field, sub angular to rounded pebbles and cobbles were seen in a thick layer. A surface scatter of pottery is located all around this stupa.	Late centuries B.C.E.to early centuries C.E. (Early Historic)	Deo & Joshi, 1972
Suleman Tekdi	PNI01.III	Pauni	20.771750	79.635730	Religious (Stupa)	Structural feature	Extant structural remains. Surface visibility limited due to dense vegetation. However, a few brick bats were visible in the nala channel and at a few places on the slope of the structure. The visibility was 10-15%. The site is characterised by a huge mound like which is possibly a brick line stupa. The structure is disturbed by the heavy growth of vegetation due to poor preservation and conservation. The site is covered with very dense vegetation cover. A few brick courses exposed by the erosion inside the channel were visible in the west of the structure.	Late centuries B.C.E.to early centuries C.E. (Early Historic)	Deo & Joshi, 1972
Prabhat Pattan (North)	PPT01.I	Prabhat Pattan	21.646720	78.268000	Settlement	Habitation mound and sculptures	At this plot a few sculptural remains that have come out of agricultural fields have been placed near a modern Mata temple. In addition to this, lot of pottery belonging to Early Historic, Vakataka and medieval Period have been encountered in this agricultural field. This site does not preserve any thick habitation layers and whatever superficial deposit is encountered seems to be very disturbed. The sculptural remains seen near this site are broken basalt images of Nandi, Ganesha etc.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-2nd millennium C.E. (Early Historic to medieval)	None. New Discovery
Prabhat Pattan (Shiv)	PPT01.II	Prabhat Pattan	21.649720	78.259640	Spot find (Displaced sculptural)	Sculpture	At this place a part of some medieval sculpture that contains a horse and a female. It has been installed on a small mound. Local legend says that this is the image of a women and a horse that turned into stone. This area does not have any sort of habitation deposit.	Mid-2nd millennium C.E. (medieval)	None. New Discovery
Prabhat Pattan (West)	PPT01.III	Prabhat Pattan	21.648250	78.264890	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	At this place some habitation deposit with pottery is seen.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Prabhat Pattan (South)	PPT01.IV	Prabhat Pattan	21.638560	78.269720	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	This area has a extensive habitation deposit belonging to Early Historic and Vakataka Period. The mound is used as agricultural field as well as a sizable part of the present settlement is also located on it. The extent of the visible scatter is about 500x500 meters.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Narasimha Temple	RTK01	Ramtek	21.397638	79.334076	Religious	Surface scatter, carved architectural remains	Two temples, one still standing, and one only visible as foundations in the topsoil. Standing structure houses large sculptural image of Narasimha	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Cunningham, 1878; Shastri, 1997
Ramtek	RTK02	Ramtek	21.407253	79.338041	Settlement	Habitation mound, exposed sections, surface scatter	Multiple areas of habitation deposit and surface scatters of archaeological material located at the base of the Northern slope of Ramtek Hill. Associated remains also visible in various cuts on the hill itself.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-2nd millennium C.E. (Early Historic to medieval)	Lacey, 2016
Ritpur (Riddhpur)	RTP01	Ritpur	21.239470	77.806890	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	This is a famous religious centre and an annual fair is organized in the month of March. This is an old medieval settlement, which is located on about 2 meters thick Early Historic and Vakataka deposit. It appears that the expanse of the deposit is more than ten acres. At present the thickest part of this habitation deposit is located near the Government school and the Muslim graveyard.	Late centuries B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Early Historic and Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Samudrapur Reeth	SMD01	Samudrapur	20.649390	78.968220	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	The site is located near the Hanuman temple in Rajurwadi area. This area is under cultivation and a small rivulet passes north of this area. The area is about 150m x 200 meters. The deposit is not very thick but a high frequency of pottery is visible across the surface.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	None. New Discovery
Sangarhi	SNG01	Sangarhi	20.967580	79.975960	Settlement	Structural features	A small medieval fortress is located nearby water tank. In the village a medieval temple and some potsherds of medieval period were noted.	Mid-2nd millennium C.E. (medieval)	None. New Discovery
Sasra	SSR01	Sasara	20.972440	79.954390	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	The habitation deposit of Sasra is about 3m thick. The surface of the mound is obscured by the present settlement of Sasra. The extent of the mound is more than 10 acres. Towards south west of the village 3 large water tanks can be seen, possibly these are parts of abundant course of the river. The surface of the site is covered with lots of iron slag.	1st millennium B.C.E.to mid-1st millennium C.E. (Iron Age to Vakataka)	None. New Discovery

Site Name	Site Code	Village Name	North	East	Site Type	Features	Description	Date Range	References
Sati Tola	STL01	Chakaheti	21.636640	79.723830	Spot find (Sati stone)	Sculptures	Many hero and sati stones are seen erected on rectangular platforms.	Mid-2nd millennium C.E. (medieval)	None. New Discovery
Teegaon	TGN01	Teegaon	21.641810	78.457970	Settlement	Habitation mound and structural features	The site is defined by a small habitation mound and surface material dating to the Vakataka and early medieval period. Towards the northern fringes of the village a Late medieval Dutt temple can be seen located on the right bank of the river Jam.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. to mid-2nd millennium (Vakataka to medieval)	None. New Discovery
Tirodi	TRD01	Tirodi	21.685920	79.719220	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	The site is defined by a small habitation mound and surface material dating to the Vakataka and early medieval period. Villagers state that the copper plate was discovered in the mining area from where lots of broken earthen utensils were found.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. to mid-2nd millennium (Vakataka to medieval)	None. New Discovery
Wag	WAG01	Wag	20.936750	79.437310	Settlement	Habitation mound and surface scatter	About 100x100 meters of habitation deposit belonging to the Vakataka period was seen on the western fringes of the village near the primary school. This is part of a much larger habitation mound that is partially obscured by the modern village.	Mid-1st millennium C.E. (Vakataka)	Sali, 1998

Discussion

Having identified the locations of all of these sites, it is now possible to turn to consider the ways in which the practice of issuing land grants with copperplate charters was related to the wider societal and cultural dynamics that existed around them. The pilot nature of this survey does, of course, limit what we can say about the sites that were found. Yet, this necessary first stage of reconnaissance, undertaken to test the viability of this approach as an archaeological point of departure, does indicate where more systematic surveys can be carried out, at which point we can begin to make detailed observations about the activities that took place at individual sites, and identify patterns in those activities at local and regional scales. Until such investigations can be carried out, however, the basic features of the sites that were identified (their physical and chronological extents, and broad categorisations of site type), and their locations in relation to the find spots of the copperplate charters, nevertheless enable us to make some interesting observations. First, it is significant that well-established settlement sites were encountered at, or in the immediate vicinity of, the find spots of all of the copperplate charters that were surveyed. On a theoretical level, this reinforces the point that these charters did not exist in abstraction. They were irrefutably products of a particular societal and cultural framework, and so are as much part of the archaeological landscape as the archaeological sites that surround them and inhabit the same space.

It is also significant that the majority of the settlements that were encountered during this pilot study had long site histories—many with much earlier Iron Age (or “megalithic”) foundations. That the Vidarbha region has such a deep history is well known, at least in archaeological circles. Pre- and proto-historic sites have been noted here for well over a century (Hislop 1857), and the region is home to the largest concentration of early Iron Age sites in the subcontinent (see Mohanty & Thakuria 2014). To date, much of the scholarship on the copperplates and the history of that slightly later historical period have not really taken this into account in their consideration of the presence of the eastern Vakatakas and practice of land grants in the region. In part, and speaking generally, this can be explained in terms of the ever-widening gap between archaeological and historic scholarship; as well as by the fact that when scholarship on the Vakatakas has attempted to consider them from a longer chronological perspective, they have done so only with reference to the dynasty that immediately preceded them: the Satavahannas. However, it is one thing to know, intellectually, that the region has a deep history, but quite another to know that the places associated with copperplate charters occupied exactly those same spaces as the earlier sites.¹⁹ This association forces us to adopt a much deeper chronological perspective in our consideration of the copperplate charters. This in turn has clear implications for how we think about the charters and interpret the practice

and effects of land grants—especially when we remember that the charters are frequently thought of as reflecting the colonisation of parts of Vidarbha by the eastern Vakatakas. Excavations at some of the settlements associated with the find spots of the charters, such as Mahurjhari (Deo 1973; Mohanty 2002, 2003) and Pauni (Deo & Joshi 1972; Nath 1998), like those at a number of other sites across the region, have revealed large and complex settlements that were thriving centres of production connected to extensive networks of inter-regional trade and exchange throughout the first millennium B.C.E. and early centuries C.E.²⁰ When considered in this light it is difficult to conceive of any sort of colonisation of the area through granting land, or that these grants were in some way instigated or caused agrarian activity, which in every instance may have already been well established.

It is also possible (if somewhat more tentatively) to discern a degree of variation in the settlement archaeology associated with the copperplates. If we look at the basic characteristic features of these settlements as they appear on the surface we can see that they vary widely in terms of their extent and morphology. We can, for instance, identify both fortified settlements such as Adam (ADM01) and Pauni (PNI01), as well as non-fortified settlements, which account for the majority of settlements in the area. All of these differ in terms of size, and there is no correlation between site size and whether they are fortified. Variation can also be identified in terms of the number and types of sites that are associated with the find spots of the copper plates. If we look at the distribution of these settlements (see Fig. 6), we can see that the number at or surrounding copperplate find spots differs considerably across the region. The highest number of settlements appears to cluster in the core eastern part of the region, around the copperplate sites of Jamb, Mahurjhari, Mandhal, Mansar and Miregaon. The sites of Jamb and Mandhal in particular all have at least three large citadels and/or settlements within a 3km radius, which is indicative of a high degree of settlement density; in the western sector there are fewer settlements at or surrounding the copperplate sites. This trend is also reflected in the distribution of religious sites, which also exhibit variation in terms of the religious groups associated with the sites that are recorded.

While we cannot say much more at this stage, these variations indicate a degree of diversity of wider settlement patterns and scales of urbanism across the region. This has implications for how we think about the practice of land grants, as we can imagine the effects of such practice to have been very different in relation to factors such as settlement density, differential levels of agricultural activity, local networks of exchange, and systems of administration. None of these factors, at least in as much as they are reflected by the distribution of sites, can necessarily be thought of as being the same across the region.

Conclusions

There are, of course, far more detailed observations that we would like to be able to make in order to fully expand on the societal and cultural contexts within which the charters existed. This will only be possible after further archaeological work in the area. There are any number of ways in which this could proceed, including, but by no means limited to: landscape surveys of the wider region incorporating both areas surrounding the find spots of copperplate charters and those where no charters are recorded; detailed site surveys and excavations of individual sites (including settlements and religious complexes) using suitable methods; and a considerable investment in the investigation of both environmental and geoarchaeological remains.

However, from the evidence that has been generated by this pilot study we can clearly see that the copperplate charters have both an archaeological and geographical context. Admittedly, the archaeological contexts that have been considered here only apply to one region: Vidarbha. Yet, it would be surprising if the trends noted here were not mirrored in other regions. The fact that these charters are known and have been studied in historical scholarship for over one hundred and fifty years without any recognition of or reference to these archaeological contexts, which are readily apparent, highlights the disjuncture between textual historical and archaeological scholarship. This disjuncture, together with the fact that the copperplates are demonstrably part of an archaeological landscape, shows that it is both necessary to look at these wider contexts and demonstrates the clear value in doing so. Examining the settings of these the charters potentially allows us to reconstruct a richer and more detailed account of the societal and cultural framework within which they existed. Crucially, it enables such a framework to be constructed from the evidence most directly associated with the charters, rather than that derived from other settings and environments, which may have little (if anything) to do with the texts with which they are being related. Indeed, it is arguably only through such means that we can not only focus on topics that have so far only been considered from textual and art historical bases in much more meaningful ways,²¹ but also fully assess the role and impact of the copperplate charters. Given their importance as both inscriptions that record the practice of land grants in their texts, and objects that embody a series of wider dynamics and processes, this is surely of prime concern.

The value of taking an archaeological approach to the study of the copperplate charters not only extends to improving our understanding of this important data set. On one level, we do not need to limit ourselves to the copperplates. It is equally important to investigate the archaeological and geographical settings of other epigraphic material—something that in many instances would be even less problematic given the easily identifiable provenience of inscriptions carved on extant architectural remains. Nor

should taking an archaeological approach to the study of inscriptions only extend as far as consideration of their contexts. Other factors, such as the materiality of inscriptions also need to be taken into account, even if at the basic level of initiating conversations about the materials and objects that were used in their production. Doing so would add a useful dimension to our understanding of the meanings, significance and value of the inscriptions for the people that used them; and enable us to make inferences about the ways they were used and how they worked as objects in the negotiation of social relations—all, ultimately, bringing us closer to an understanding the people that used them.

Equally, while certainly of considerable importance, the purpose of investing the study of the copperplate charters with an archaeological approach is not simply to augment textual scholarship. Given how (relatively) little archaeology of historic periods has been carried out across South Asia, there is clearly a need to reinvigorate the archaeological approach to those periods more generally (Hawkes 2014). This would necessarily involve the archaeological investigation of sites and objects that are not related to the epigraphic record at all. Ultimately, this raises a much wider concern (or set of concerns) involving: the relationships between both archaeology and texts, and archaeological and historical scholarship in the study of South Asia's past; and the need for the discipline of archaeology to formulate its own set of methods and theories for the investigation of historical periods. None of these are going to be resolved over night. Yet, as the results of this pilot study indicate, it is arguably the case that concentrating our efforts on the areas where archaeology and text intersect will not only open up fruitful avenues for further research, but also provide the means with which we can negotiate these issues.

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Endnotes

¹ This figure is based on the reports of inscriptions in the main published sources (e.g. the volumes of *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, *Epigraphia Indica*, as well as syntheses of regional material). Though due to various factors surrounding the ways in which historical scholarship

has been (and continues to be) organised and practiced, reports of particular epigraphic, sculptural and archaeological remains is often confined to local region-specific literature where they become difficult to access from outside that region, and are rarely related to other material from other regions. The existence of such “information silos” makes it difficult to put a precise total on the number of copperplates in existence. This is compounded by the fact that new discoveries continue to be made (e.g. Dubey and Acharya 2014; Tripathy 2005), which unless they are published in journals (as opposed to simply being listed in unpublished reports) will remain unknown to the majority of scholars working on South Asia. Also note, this figure does not include those copper plate inscriptions that record “land sales” (as opposed to land grants) found in West Bengal and Bangladesh, as for the purposes of this study they are classed as a separate and discrete corpus of evidence.

² Proponents of the feudal model cite the fact that the very existence of these charters was itself a proof of the fragmentation of a (assumed) centralized political authority that had characterized the earlier “ancient” polities of North India. Those who rejected this model frequently cited the fact that most grants were made to temples not political subordinates and could, therefore, not be taken as reflecting any form of shift in political authority or system of governance.

³ The dynamics between textual history and archaeology are the subject of a great deal of scholarship both in South Asia and throughout the world, and need not be rearticulated here. For useful overviews, see André (1998), Moreland (2001), Ray & Sinopoli (2004).

⁴ That archaeologists working in South Asia have tended to focus on earlier prehistoric periods for at least the last sixty years is readily apparent from even the most cursory review of the published literature—quite simply, the amount of prehistoric sites that are excavated and surveyed outnumber those from early historic and later periods—and is well attested to elsewhere (Chakrabarti 2012). This focus on early periods is also manifest in the widely shared goal of fixing the maximum chronological extent of a site (whatever type of “site” that might be) when it is excavated. This in turn has informed the choice of where to dig, with excavation trenches generally placed in locations perceived to represent the earliest areas of occupation or use within a site, with the deepest stratigraphy. The unintentional consequence of such practice is that areas with later phases of occupation or use within that same site are missed, and may not be excavated at all.

⁵ At most settlements with later (i.e. “Gupta period” and early medieval) phases of occupation, the areas that have been excavated account for less than 2% of the total area of the site (see Hawkes 2014). Thus, whatever might be seen, archaeologically, in those small areas cannot necessarily be

taken as representative of what took place across the wider site. It need hardly be added that the “box” and “grid” system developed by Mortimer Wheeler was only ever intended as a crude but expedient means of evaluating the archaeological potential of a site prior to full excavation (see Wheeler 1954).

⁶ With the common goal of many excavations being to fix the “cultural sequence” of a site, they tend to be excavated and recorded “in section” with particular attention paid to the stratigraphy visible in section as opposed to, and rarely in conjunction with, excavating and recording “in plan”—that is: horizontally, with sensitivity to subtle changes in the archaeological matrix that are not always conveniently visible in the section of the trench.

⁷ For instance: a hoard of 28 charters issued by the Valkha dynasty was found buried in a metal chest in Risavala, Madhya Pradesh (Ramesh and Tewari 1990); seven copperplate charters were found in an underground chamber near a water tank in the village of tank in Palitana, Gujarat (Konow 1912); the Abhayagiri copperplate inscription was found in the structure of a vihara at Anuradhapura (Wickremasinghe 1904); and three inscriptions were found suspended by an iron rod across the rim of the urn, and preserved by rice husks in an urn in the village of Andhavaram in Odisha (Subrahmanyam 1958).

⁸ Though, of course, the charters could have been deposited at any point in time, and need not have been deposited by people who knew and understood their original meaning and importance. That is not to say they would cease to have been significant. They may have continued to have some sort of cultural currency by virtue of their materiality or antiquity, though reconstructing what significance this may have been is, of course, difficult without an understanding of the precise archaeological context they were deposited in.

⁹ Grant awarded by the Leverhulme Trust in 2011, and research carried out between 2011-2014.

¹⁰ An interactive map showing the locations of the copperplate charters, along with other contemporary inscriptions in stone, together with a brief précis of the content of each inscription are being posted online at: http://www.britishmuseum.org/research/research_projects/all_current_projects/beyond_boundaries/inscriptions_and_sites.aspx

¹¹ In this connection, it should be stressed that with this data being posted online it is now possible for all interested scholars to interrogate it and examine the spatial distribution of these charters for themselves.

¹² In this connection it is important to note the existence of early copperplate charters issued by the first Pallava dynasty. The precise dating of many of the early Pallava inscriptions is still a matter of debate (Brocquet 1998, Mahalingam 1988, Francis 2013), but it would appear that the earliest charters issued by the earliest Pallava dynasty date to the fourth

century C.E., contemporary to those issued by the Guptas. Here, we can cite the Gunapadeya plates of Charudevi (Hultsch 1906), the Hirahadagalli plates of Skandavarman (Bühler 1892), and the Mayidavolu plates of Siva Skandavarman (Hultsch 1902). However, the text of these earliest Pallava charters is inscribed in both Prakrit and Sanskrit, and their composition does not follow the same general pattern as those from other regions, or the later charters from the same region. As such, their early appearance in this region is considered a parallel development, separate from (though undoubtedly related to) the main thrust of this new tradition that does seem to have owed its inception to the Guptas.

¹³ For a useful discussion of the scholarship on this topic, see Kulke's (2004) synopsis of the nature of the state and process of state formation under the eastern Vakatakas.

¹⁴ In this region, the early Iron Age is generally considered to span from the early first millennium to the fourth century B.C.E. For a useful review of previous archaeological investigations in the region, see Sawant (2010).

¹⁵ Cf. early discussion of Nagardhan in Wellstead (1834).

¹⁶ Surveys were carried out using the locations of modern villages (in this instance, the villages where copperplate charters were found) as the main foci of enquiry, and then using local informants in conjunction with fieldwalking of the modern settlements and surrounding areas to locate archaeological features and remains. Once localities were found, then they were systematically fieldwalked in regular transects to fix their extent, and representative samples of surface remains (if present) were collected to help date the sites. Due to limitations of time and access, it was not possible to survey the find-spots of Balaghat, Dudia, Siwani, Mohalla and Yavatmal.

¹⁷ Settlement sites were noted at the villages (and towns) of Bellora, Jamb, Mahurhari, Mandhal, Meeregaon, Pauni, Pattan, Ridhapur, Teegaon, Tirodi, and Washim.

¹⁸ This was the case with copperplate find spots of Chamak, Mansar and Wadgaon.

¹⁹ Of course, the traditional view, which (at least in South Asia) owes a great deal to early Orientalist imaginings of continuity and the immutable Indian village (e.g. Gans 1837), would have us believe that everything occupies an older site of some description. This stance is lent further validation by the uncritical application of wider landscape theory and awareness that almost everything in the landscape can, depending on one's research objectives and frame of reference, be defined as a "site". Yet, as it has been made clear, any such observations have little meaning or substance unless we are equipped with enough archaeological understanding to interpret them. In other words, we might "know" at some level that things came before, but we cannot say very much about them unless we have a basic grasp of the archaeological realities of that place.

²⁰ For details of excavations at other large and noteworthy settlements in other locations throughout the region, see, for example, Bopardikar (1996), Deo (1970), Deo and Jamkhedkar (1982), Dikshit (1968), Mishra et al. (2016).

²¹ For instance, topics such as the ways in which the copperplates relate to the history of the Hindu temple and the practice of resident deities being recipients of gifts of land, or the examination of the emergence and spread of temple institutions as agents for land ownership and management, all represent significant thrusts of historical research over recent years that would both benefit from a thorough grounding in archaeological realities.

বিষয়সংক্ষেপ

চতুর্থ থেকে সপ্তম শতক পর্যন্ত 'গুপ্ত যুগ' হিসাবে সমধিক পরিচিত সময়কালকে দক্ষিণ এশিয়ার ইতিহাসে গঠন প্রদানকারী কালপর্ব হিসাবে বিবেচনা করা হয়। লিখিত উৎস নির্ভর ইতিহাস চর্চায় বিভিন্ন লিপির পঠন ও ব্যাখ্যাকে গুরুত্ব প্রদান করা হয়েছে। এই লিপিগুলো এই সময়ের সবচাইতে বৃহত্তম উৎস। বিশেষকরে, তাম্রপট্টগুলো ভীষণ তাৎপর্যপূর্ণ হিসাবে প্রমাণিত হয়েছে। এগুলো ব্রাহ্মণদের ও মন্দিরের মতন প্রতিষ্ঠানগুলোতে ভূমিদানই কেবল নয়, বরং ওই সময়ের বৃহত্তর রাজনৈতিক বৈধতা পাওয়ার, ধর্মীয় রূপান্তরের ও সামাজিক-অর্থনৈতিক বদলের প্রক্রিয়াগুলোকেও এই লিপিগুলো ধারণ করছে। এপর্যন্ত, এসব লিপির লেখা নিয়ে আলোচনার তাই মুখ্য থেকেছে। কোন পরিপ্রেক্ষিতে এই লিপিগুলো লিখিত হয়েছিল আর কোন পরিপ্রেক্ষিতে এই লিপিগুলো ব্যবহৃত হত তা অনালোচিতই থেকে গেছে। এই প্রবন্ধে এসব লিপি নিয়ে আলোচনায় প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক দৃষ্টিভঙ্গিকে প্রাধান্য দেয়া হয়েছে। এই প্রবন্ধে এই লিপিগুলোর ভৌগোলিক ও প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক প্রেক্ষিতকে পর্যালোচনা করা হয়েছে, প্রথমত, উপমহাদেশে এমন লিপিগুলোর বিস্তৃতির মানচিত্রায়ন করে; দ্বিতীয়ত, বিদর্ভের মত একটি অঞ্চলে এধরনের লিপিগুলোর প্রাপ্তিস্থানের প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক অনুসঙ্গ পর্যালোচনা করার মাধ্যমে। এই গবেষণার ফলাফল এই লিপিগুলোসহ অন্যান্য লিপিগুলোর ভবিষ্যৎ পর্যালোচনায় স্পষ্ট ভূমিকা রাখবে। ঐতিহাসিক কালপর্বের প্রত্নতাত্ত্বিক গবেষণায়ও নতুন দিগন্ত উন্মোচন করবে।

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